

Water Depth Prediction in Stormwater Sewers Using Deep Learning Method

Jasmina Moskovljević^{1, 2} [0009-0003-5737-0184], Luka Vinokić¹ [0009-0001-1879-430X], Anja Randelović² [0000-0002-0804-8928], Željko Vasilic² [0000-0002-9574-4509], Milan Dotlic¹ [0000-0003-2246-575X], Zoran Vojinovic³ [0000-0002-7601-4041], Nataša Manojlović⁴ [], Veljko Prodanović^{1, 5} [0000-0002-3800-0765]

¹ Institute for Artificial Intelligence R&D of Serbia, Fruškogorska 1, Novi Sad 21000, Serbia

jasmina.moskovljevic@ivi.ac.rs
luka.vinokic@ivi.ac.rs
milan.dotlic@ivi.ac.rs
veljko.prodanovic@ivi.ac.rs

² Faculty of Civil Engineering, University of Belgrade, Belgrade 11000, Serbia

arandjelovic@grf.bg.ac.rs
zvasilic@grf.bg.ac.rs

³ Department of Environmental Engineering and Water Technology, IHE-Delft, Westvest 7, 2611 AX Delft, the Netherlands

z.vojinovic@un-ihe.org

⁴ Wasserbau, Hamburg University of Technology, 21073 Hamburg, Germany

natasa.manojlovic@tuhh.de

⁵ School of Civil and Environmental Engineering, University of New South Wales (UNSW), Sydney 2052, NSW, Australia

Abstract. Accurate prediction of water depth in urban drainage systems is essential for effective flood risk mitigation and sustainable urban water management. This paper presents a deep learning model based on Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) architecture for forecasting water depth in a stormwater sewer, tested on a part of Belgrade's stormwater system in Serbia. The model uses high-resolution rainfall time series and hydraulic simulation data from SWMM model to predict water levels with 5-minute temporal resolution. A comprehensive hyperparameter sensitivity analysis was conducted using the One-at-a-time (OAT) method to systematically optimize the model architecture and training parameters. The results demonstrate that the optimized LSTM model achieved a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.95 for 5-minute-ahead predictions, showing strong performance in short-term forecasting while maintaining computational efficiency. The study identifies the optimal network configuration with 128 neurons, ReLU activation function and learning rate of 0.001 after testing and validation. These findings highlight LSTM's superior capability to model complex rainfall-runoff relationships in urban environments, providing valuable tools for real-time stormwater management and enhanced flood early warning systems.

Keywords: water depth, stormwater sewer, LSTM.

1 Introduction

Climate change is leading to more frequent and intense extreme weather events, while urbanization is increasing the amount of impermeable surfaces in cities. Together, these changes contribute to a higher risk of urban flooding, which is why effective stormwater management and flood risk prediction are becoming increasingly important for planning and improving urban areas.

Urbanized areas such as New Belgrade face numerous challenges in controlling and draining stormwater due to high percentage of impervious surfaces, limited natural infiltration and existing infrastructure that often isn't designed to handle increasingly frequent and intense rainfall events. These limitations highlight the urgent need for improved stormwater management strategies and reliable flood prediction systems.

Traditional hydrological and hydraulic models have long been used to simulate urban drainage behavior. One of the most widely applied tools is the Storm Water Management Model (SWMM), developed by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency [1]. SWMM is a dynamic rainfall–runoff simulation model that enables detailed representation of urban drainage systems, including surface runoff, flow routing through pipe networks, and storage within system components such as manholes and retention structures. In this research, SWMM is used to generate data on water levels in manholes under various rainfall scenarios, providing a controlled and physically consistent dataset for further analysis.

Machine learning models have already proven effective in various hydrological settings, offering reliable forecasting and modeling of the hydrological responses of the urban drainage system [2, 3].

This research develops an LSTM neural network that simulates water levels based on input rainfall data and water levels in manholes obtained through SWMM modeling. The study also includes sensitivity analysis of neural network hyperparameters to identify those with significant impact on model performance.

The research is guided by the following key questions: i) Can an LSTM model accurately reproduce water level dynamics in an urban drainage system based on rainfall input data? ii) Which hyperparameters have the greatest impact on the predictive performance of the LSTM model?

By addressing these questions, the study aims to contribute to the development of efficient, data-driven tools for urban flood prediction and to support more resilient and sustainable urban water management practices.

2 Method and material

2.1 Study area

The study area is in Block 13, New Belgrade, and covers approximately 50 hectares. About 70% of the catchment consists of streets, buildings and parking lots, while the remainder consists of green areas and parks. The stormwater sewer system drains

gravitationally into the sewer network and collected water is pumped from the pumping station to the Danube River. Drainage area is outlined with a red line in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Drainage area in Block 13 in New Belgrade.

2.2 Long short-term memory (LSTM)

Compared to standard neural networks, RNNs differ in the way information is propagated. In conventional neural networks, information flows in a single direction, from input to output, whereas RNNs feed information back into the network at each time step. As a result, Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) are designed to process sequential data by using feedback connections that allow information from previous inputs to influence the current output. In theory, RNNs can store representations of recent input events through their activations. However, in practice, standard RNNs struggle with learning long-term dependencies. As sequences become longer, information from earlier time steps gradually disappears due to the vanishing or exploding gradient problem, making it difficult for the network to retain meaningful long-term information [4].

Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks were introduced to address this limitation. LSTM is a specialized RNN architecture that uses memory cells and gating mechanisms to maintain a constant error flow through time. This design enables LSTMs to learn long-term dependencies over hundreds or even thousands of time steps, while still preserving the ability to model short-term patterns [5].

Due to these characteristics, LSTM networks are well suited for modeling the hydrological response of urban drainage systems, where both short-term variability and long-term dependencies are important.

In this study, a simple LSTM architecture with a single hidden layer was used to keep the model computationally efficient while still capturing the main temporal patterns in the data. This choice is appropriate since the input variables (precipitation and SWMM-simulated water levels) already contain meaningful physical information, so deeper network layers are not necessary. Adding more layers would mainly increase model complexity and the risk of overfitting, without clear improvements in performance given the limited dataset. The number of neurons (128) was selected based on a hyperparameter sensitivity analysis, showing a good balance between performance, stability, and computational cost.

2.3 Data

The input data for the LSTM model consist of precipitation measurements and water depths in manholes obtained from the SWMM simulations, while the model is trained to predict future water depths in the manholes. The sewer network in the study area consists of 380 conduits and 378 nodes.

Fig. 2. Subcatchment structure in Block 13 in SWMM [6].

Rainfall data recorded at the main meteorological station in Belgrade ($\varphi = 44.80^\circ$; $\lambda = 20.47^\circ$; elevation = 132 m above sea level) were analyzed for the period from April 11, 2018, to May 7, 2020. The data has a temporal resolution of 5 minutes, which allows for a highly detailed monitoring of both the intensity and duration of rainfall events. This high-resolution dataset is particularly important for identifying short-duration,

high-intensity rainfall, which can have significant adverse effects in urban areas due to rapid runoff and potential flooding.

The dataset also includes extreme events, with the highest rainfall peaks observed in July 2018 and July 2019, which are relevant for assessing the resilience and capacity of the urban drainage system under intense rainfall events.

Fig. 3. Precipitation (mm) – period from 11.04.2018 to 07.05.2020.

2.4 Training, validation and testing process

The workflow (see. Fig. 4) of this study includes a case study setup, preparation of precipitation and water-level datasets, and preprocessing through data trimming. An LSTM deep learning model is then trained, followed by hyperparameter sensitivity analysis. Finally, the model performance is evaluated using metrics such as RMSE, R^2 , and maximum error.

Fig. 4. Flowchart for Development of an LSTM model for sewer water depth prediction.

Data Preprocessing. Long periods without rainfall and with constant water levels were removed to focus on periods with actual changes, improving model training efficiency and convergence speed. The function automatically ignored all initial zero values until the first rainfall event and retained maximum 288 consecutive zeros after each recorded rainfall (equivalent to one day at 5-minute resolution).

Fig. 5. Example of trimming a rainfall period. Grey areas showing data kept for model training, while white areas showing discarded periods without rainfall.

Input windows size formation. The input window size represents the sum of the number of past time steps (lag variable) and the number of future time steps for which a forecast is made (horizon variable). In this study, the forecast horizon is 3-time steps (3×5 minutes), while values from the previous 6-time steps (6×5 minutes) are considered. Fig. 6 shows an example of how the input window size is formed.

Fig. 6. Example of input window size formation for the LSTM model for sewer water depth prediction.

Data splitting for training, validation and testing. For this study, rainfall and water level data were divided into three datasets: training, validation and testing.

Training set covers the period from April 11, 2018, to January 1, 2020. This set forms the basis for model development and contains most of the available data (over 80% of the total time span). It allows the model to detect long-term trends, seasonal variations, and other key patterns. Validation set covers the period from January 1 to April 11, 2020. This set is used to fine-tune the model parameters and to check its stability on independent data. Test set covers the period from April 11 to May 7, 2020. This set is used exclusively for the final model evaluation, simulating real forecasting conditions.

This approach ensures that the model is not overfitted to the training data and can generate reliable predictions on completely new data.

Model performance evaluation criteria. Model performance is evaluated using the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), the coefficient of determination (R^2) and the maximum error. The evaluation is conducted on both the validation and test datasets to assess the model's predictive performance.

RMSE is a statistical measure that quantifies the average magnitude of errors between predicted and observed values. Unlike the mean absolute error, RMSE gives greater weight to larger errors, as differences are squared before averaging. A lower RMSE indicates better model accuracy. However, because differences are squared, RMSE is sensitive to extreme errors, which should be considered when interpreting results. It is calculated using the following formula [4]:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_i^n (H_i^{mod} - H_i^{obs})^2}{n}}, \quad (1)$$

where:

- H_i^{MOD} – predicted water depth at time step i ,
- H_i^{OBS} – observed water depth at time step i ,
- n – total number of data points.

The coefficient of determination (R^2) is a statistical measure that indicates how well a regression model explains the variation in the dependent variable using the independent variable. It shows the proportion of total variation in the dependent variable that can be explained by the model.

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_i^n (H_{obs,i} - H_{sim,i})^2}{\sum_i^n (H_{obs,i} - \overline{H_{obs}})^2}, \quad (2)$$

where:

- $H_{SIM,i}$ – predicted water depth at time step i ,
- $H_{OBS,i}$ – observed water depth at time step i ,
- $\overline{H_{obs}}$ – mean of all observed values $H_{OBS,i}$.

$R^2 = 1$ indicates that the model perfectly explains all variability in the observed data. In contrast, $R^2 = 0$ means that the model does not explain any of the variability and performs no better than a baseline model that always predicts the mean of the target variable.

The maximum error is a statistical measure that indicates the largest difference between predicted and observed values in the dataset. It provides information on the worst-case prediction error of the model. It is calculated as:

$$\mathbf{Max\ error} = \mathbf{max} |H_{obs,i} - H_{sim,i}|, \quad (3)$$

where:

- $H_{SIM,i}$ — predicted water depth at time step i ,
- $H_{OBS,i}$ — observed water depth at time step i .

2.5 Hyperparameter sensitivity analysis

A sensitivity analysis was performed using the One-at-a-time (OAT) method [7] to evaluate the impact of key hyperparameters on the LSTM model's performance. The analysis varied the number of neurons (32-256), dropout rate (0.1-0.5), learning rate (0.0005-0.005), number of epochs (50-400), and activation function (tanh, ReLU) while keeping other parameters constant.

Table 1. Model hyperparameters and their value ranges.

Parameter	Value Range	
Number of neurons	32	256
Dropout	0.1	0.5
Learning rate	0.0005	0.005
Number of epochs	50	400
Activation function	tanh or ReLU	

3 Results

3.1 Hyperparameter sensitivity analysis

Results showed that 128 neurons provided optimal performance, balancing model capacity and generalization. Lower dropout rates (0.1-0.2) yielded better results than higher values, indicating excessive regularization harms performance. A learning rate of 0.001 achieved the best balance between convergence speed and stability. The model converged effectively within 200 epochs, with longer training providing minimal improvements. ReLU activation consistently outperformed tanh in capturing nonlinear hydrological relationships.

The optimal configuration (128 neurons, 0.1 dropout, 0.001 learning rate, 200 epochs, ReLU) achieved $R^2 = 0.9865$ and $RMSE = 0.0050$ m on training data. This analysis demonstrates that targeted hyperparameter optimization is essential for developing efficient and accurate LSTM models for hydrological forecasting.

Fig. 7. Learning curves for hyperparameter tuning of the LSTM model: (a) number of neurons, (b) dropout rate, (c) activation function, and (d) learning rate.

3.2 Model performance

The optimized LSTM model demonstrated high precision, with the best performance achieved for the $t+1$ step (5 minutes ahead). Accuracy gradually deteriorated for the $t+2$ and $t+3$ steps, indicating that the model is more reliable for short-term forecasts. Although the model successfully captured the overall trends in the data, it was less effective in reproducing rapid fluctuations, which resulted in slight prediction delays and reduced sensitivity to sudden changes. This behavior is typical for many time-series models and indicates the need for further tuning to better capture the short-term dynamics.

Table 2 presents RMSE, R^2 , and maximum deviation values for one-, two-, and three-step ahead predictions for both training and test datasets. While RMSE and R^2 indicate consistently good overall performance, notable differences are observed in maximum errors between the two sets.

Higher maximum errors in the training set (0.4678 m, 1.4476 m, and 1.9822 m for t+1, t+2, and t+3) are associated with rare extreme events (peak water levels) present in the training data. These events involve rapid changes in water levels that are more difficult for the model to capture, resulting in larger deviations.

In contrast, the test set does not include comparable extreme events, leading to significantly lower maximum errors (0.0067 m, 0.0182 m, and 0.0229 m). This suggests strong model performance under normal conditions, but reduced sensitivity to rare extremes, which are more challenging to generalize in data-driven models.

Table 2. RMSE, R^2 and maximum deviation values in one-step, two-step and three-step ahead predictions for the training and test datasets.

time prediction	Training			Test		
	RMSE [m]	R^2 [-]	MAX [m]	RMSE [m]	R^2 [-]	MAX [m]
t+1	0.0050	0.9865	0.4678	0.0013	0.9815	0.0067
t+2	0.0111	0.9344	1.4476	0.0016	0.9694	0.0182
t+3	0.0194	0.7992	1.9822	0.0023	0.9405	0.0229

Fig. 8 presents the regression lines produced by the LSTM model alongside the 45° reference line for 1-step, 2-step, and 3-step ahead forecasts, while Fig. 9 presents the water level graph of observed and predicted values for each forecasting horizon in the test set.

The time plot confirms this pattern, i.e. at the t+1 step the predicted values closely follow the observed series with minimal deviations, remaining within a narrow interval from approximately 71.92 to 71.99. This tight clustering reflects the model's excellent short-term accuracy, further supported by the fact that most points lie along the 45° line. As the forecast horizon extends to t+2 and t+3, the deviations increase slightly, and the range of values widens, most notably for t+3, which is consistent with the expected accumulation of error in multi-step prediction.

Fig. 8. Regression line obtained by the LSTM model and the 45° line (ideal prediction); a) 1-step ahead forecast (5 minutes ahead) with the test dataset, b) 2-step ahead forecast (10 minutes ahead) with the test dataset, c) 3-step ahead forecast (15 minutes ahead) with the test dataset.

Fig. 9. Water level graph of observed and forecasted values for the test set with the LSTM prediction model a) 1-step ahead (5 minutes ahead), b) 2-steps ahead (10 minutes ahead), c) 3-steps ahead (15 minutes ahead).

4 Conclusions

The LSTM model demonstrated strong performance in predicting water depths in a stormwater network, achieving high accuracy and stability in short-term forecasts. The obtained results ($R^2 = 0.94$ and $RMSE = 0.0023$) indicate that the model effectively captures the dominant temporal patterns in the system.

As expected, the highest accuracy was achieved for the $t+1$ prediction horizon, where predicted values closely follow observed data. This is due to the lower uncertainty associated with short-term forecasting. A gradual decrease in performance was observed for $t+2$ and $t+3$ steps, which is consistent with the behavior of most time-series models, as errors accumulate and uncertainty increases with forecast distance.

Despite overall good performance, the model shows certain limitations. Its accuracy decreases when predicting more complex and rapidly changing conditions, indicating reduced sensitivity to sudden variations in the system dynamics. In addition, a systematic bias was observed during low-flow periods, where the model tends to slightly overestimate water levels. This behavior is mainly attributed to data imbalance and the smoothing effect of the MSE loss function, further reinforced by reduced representation of prolonged low-flow conditions in the dataset.

The model is also primarily based on rainfall and water level data, which limits its ability to capture broader climatic influences and restricts its applicability for long-term or climate-driven analyses.

These findings suggest that while the model is suitable for short-term operational forecasting, further improvements are needed for more complex applications. Future research could focus on incorporating additional hydrological and climatic variables, as well as exploring advanced architectures such as Graph Neural Networks (GNN) and Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINN), which may better represent spatial and physical processes in urban drainage systems.

5 Acknowledgment

The research presented herein is part of the DIGIDRAIN project (funding from the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, research program DIASPORA 2023: joint research, under grant agreement number: 17823 – City-scale digital twins for urban drainage systems: bringing “smart” to water infrastructure).

The research presented herein received financial support from the European Union’s Horizon Europe project ARTIFACT, under Grant Agreement 101159480.

References

1. Agency, U.S.E.P. *Storm Water Management Model (SWMM)*. 1971; Available from: <https://www.epa.gov/water-research/storm-water-management-model-swmm>.
2. Yang, Y. and T.F.M. Chui, *Modeling and interpreting hydrological responses of sustainable urban drainage systems with explainable machine learning methods*. Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci., 2021. **25**(11): p. 5839-5858.
3. Vinokic Luka, D.M., Prodanovic Veljko, Kolakovic Slobodan, Simonovic P. Slobodan, Stojkovic Milan, *Effectiveness of three machine learning models for prediction of daily streamflow and uncertainty assessment*. Water Research X, 2025.
4. Géron, A., *Hands-On Machine Learning with Scikit-Learn, Keras, and TensorFlow SECOND EDITION Concepts, Tools, and Techniques to Build Intelligent Systems*. 2019: O'Reilly Media, Inc.
5. Hochreiter, S. and J. Schmidhuber, *Long Short-Term Memory*. Neural Computation, 1997. **9**: p. 1735-1780.

6. Vinokić, L., et al., *Digital Twins of Urban Drainage Systems: ML-assisted algorithm for processing sensor data*. 2025.
7. Rhian Taylor, V.O., Ivan Martino, Giuseppe Nicosia, *Sensitivity Analysis for Deep Learning: Ranking Hyper-parameter Influence*, in *33rd International Conference on Tools with Artificial Intelligence (ICTAI 2021)*. 2021. p. 512-516.